

Truths to be Told: Protein, Veggies, and Carbs for Culinary Sustainability

The intricate relationship between personal well-being and the health of our planet calls for mindful choices that can shape a healthier future. This essay delves into the impact of meat consumption, the benefits of vegetables, the misconceptions surrounding carbohydrates, and the path to sustainable living.

Rethinking Meat Consumption

Traditionally, meat has been hailed as the primary source of protein. However, emerging evidence suggests that our bodies require less protein than previously believed and that plant-based foods can easily fulfill our protein needs. **Metabolizing meat protein results in the production of nitrogenous waste¹**, which can strain the liver and kidneys. Moreover, the metabolism of methionine found in meat can lead to increased cholesterol levels and acidic blood, potentially contributing to cardiovascular and bone diseases.

Unleashing the Power of Plant-Based Nutrition and Gut Health

Embracing a diet rich in vegetables offers numerous health benefits by nurturing the microbiomes in our guts. Our complex gastrointestinal tract, specially designed for processing plant-based nutrients, coevolves with gut bacteria to extract essential nourishment.

Notably, around 70% of our immune cells reside in the gut², where they play a crucial role in defending against pathogens. Gut microbiota stimulate the production of secretory IgA, the body's defense mechanism present in mucous membranes. Additionally, these microbiota aid the liver in generating complement proteins³, which are integral components of the immune system.

The fermentation of dietary fiber by gut microbiota produces short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs)⁴ like acetate, propionate, and butyrate. SCFAs inhibit fat production, promote fatty acid oxidation⁵, enhance mitochondrial function, and optimize energy production⁶. Furthermore, SCFAs improve insulin sensitivity, facilitate glucose uptake by muscles, and possess potent anti-inflammatory properties, reducing the risk of inflammatory diseases⁷.

At this point, you may wonder, without meat, how the body can gain sufficient energy to carry on daily activities. You may be surprised to know that our body is designed to rely on carbohydrates as the main source of energy, but look out for good and bad carbs.

How Carbs are Blamed Mistakenly

Carbohydrates, often unfairly criticized for their impact on health and weight, are actually the primary energy source for our bodies. The key lies

in distinguishing between good and bad carbs. While simple carbs found in refined sugars can contribute to weight gain and chronic diseases, **complex carbohydrates** such as whole grains, starchy vegetables, and legumes **offer essential nutrients, dietary fiber, and sustained energy release⁸**.

After understanding the benefits of vegetable fiber and relying on whole, unprocessed carbs for energy, what's next? Eat less, not more.

Road to Sustainability: Intermittent Fasting and Plant-Based Whole Food Diets

Adopting intermittent fasting, which alternates between fasting and eating windows, has shown significant health benefits, including improved insulin sensitivity, weight management, cellular repair, and longevity⁹. Intermittent fasting allows the body to utilize stored, excessive energy and promotes metabolic flexibility. It also holds promise in managing prevalent illnesses like diabetes, Alzheimer's, and cancer¹⁰.

During fasting periods, after depleting glycogen, the body switches to utilizing fat as a source of energy, producing ketones. Training the cells to utilize ketones through exercise can optimize energy production. Intermittent fasting also stimulates the production of growth hormones, enhances immune capacity, and may sharpen cognitive function.

Plant-based whole food diets align well with intermittent fasting, as they help maintain a neutral blood pH, in contrast to meat consumption. Additionally, plant-based diets are recognized as sustainable choices, reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with food production.

Recent studies indicate that **intermittent fasting alone can alter the bacterial composition in the gut**, increasing beneficial bacteria¹¹ that produce SCFAs¹². This further emphasizes the synergy between intermittent fasting and a plant-based whole food diet.

Reflection

Choosing the topic of protein issues and its impact on health and sustainability was motivated by De Backer and Hudders' paper on "motivations for reducing meat intake" addressed during the lecture. My article expands further on the impact of meat protein and suggests a healthy diet based on bodily and cellular functions. Exploring this topic changed my perception of meat-based protein and inspired me to adopt a plant-based whole food diet. Our small group work and the panel discussion delved into the challenges of translating knowledge into real-life practices, which I believe stem from a lack of knowledge about the interaction between food and the human body. The class provided a holistic learning experience, fostering insights into the connections between nutrition, health, and sustainability.

1 Wu, Guoyao. 2009. *Amino acids: Metabolism, functions, and nutrition*. *Amino Acids* 37, 1-17.

2 Cai, Y. Jie. 2018. *How to Take Care of Intestine 2*. China Times Publishing Company.

3 Kieran, Mary, Tuohy, Fava, Francesca & Viola, Roberto 2014. "The way to a man's heart is through his gut microbiota"--dietary pro- and prebiotics for the management of cardiovascular risk." *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, vol. 73, no. 2.

4 Bergman, Eric. N. 1990. Energy contributions of volatile fatty acids from the gastrointestinal tract in various species. *Physiological Reviews*, 70(2).

5 Morrison, Douglas J. & Preston, Tom. 2016. Formation of short chain fatty acids by the gut microbiota and their impact on human metabolism. *Gut Microbes*, 7(3).

6 Canfora, Emanuel E., Jocken, Johan W. & Blaak, Ellen E. 2015. Short-chain fatty acids in control of body weight and insulin sensitivity. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 11.

7 Kim, Myung H., Kang, Seung G., Park, Jeong H., Yanagisawa, Masashi & Kim, Chang H. 2013. Short-chain fatty acids activate GPR41 and GPR43 on intestinal epithelial cells to promote inflammatory responses in mice. *Gastroenterology*, 145(2).

8 Slavin, Joanne. 2013. Fiber and prebiotics: mechanisms and health benefits. *Nutrients*, 5(4).

9 Ruth E. Patterson, Gail A. Laughlin, Dorothy D. Sears, Andrea Z. LaCroix, Catherine Marinac, Linda C. Gallo, Sheri J. Hartman, Loki Natarajan, Carolyn M. Senger, Maria Elena Martinez & Adriana Villasefor. 2015. Intermittent fasting and human metabolic health. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 115(8).

10 Longo, Valter D. & Mattson, Mark P. 2014. Fasting: molecular mechanisms and clinical applications. *Cell Metabolism*, 19(2).

11 Hu, Xiangwei, Xia, Kai, Dai, Minhui, Han, Xiaofeng, Yuan, Peng, Liu, Jia, Liu, Shiwei, Jia, Fuhuai, Chen, Jiayu, Jiang, Fangfang, Yu, Jieyao, Yang, Huanming, Wang, Jian, Xu, Xun, Jin, Xin, Kristiansen, Karsten, Liang, Xiao, Chen, Wei, Han, Mo & Duan, Shenglin. 2023. Intermittent fasting modulates the intestinal microbiota and improves obesity and host energy metabolism. *npj Biofilms and Microbiomes*. 9. 10.1038/s41522-023-00386-4.

12 Sonnenburg, Justin L. & Sonnenburg, Erica D. 2019. Vulnerability of the industrialized microbiota. *Science*, 366.